

Laminated Plate Theory for Thick Composites: Experimental Correlation

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ABSTRACT

A thick gr/ep laminate was fabricated and characterized using visual examination, ultrasonic testing, and mechanical testing. The [0/90]_{50S} laminate was instrumented with thermocouples, vacuum-bagged, and then cured in a miniclave. The thermocouples indicated no excessive temperature overshoot during the curing process. Photomicrographs indicated excellent quality through the thickness. Specimens were cut from the plate for quasi-static compression tests and ultrasonic tests to determine the material's 3-D elastic constants. Theoretical 3-D elastic constants for the orthotropic material were calculated using a modified laminated plate theory and compared to the measured values.

Key Words: Graphite/Epoxy; Three-Dimensional; Thick Laminate; Ultrasonic; Nondestructive Evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

Thick, laminated composite materials are gaining usage in primary load bearing structures. However, many challenging problems remain to be solved in the manufacture, nondestructive evaluation, and analysis of composites with thickness measured in centimeters rather than millimeters.

A common problem experienced during the curing of thick thermosetting laminates is an excessive temperature overshoot due to the exothermic cross-linking process. This temperature rise is most difficult to control in the interior plies of a thick laminate, particularly when the number of plies reaches the hundreds. Higher internal temperatures may lead to nonuniform curing rates which, in turn, lead to a nonuniform resin flow and fiber volume fraction through the thickness. Other common defects encountered in thick laminates are fiber waviness and excessive porosity. Hence, there is a clear need to develop a capability to manufacture thick composite laminates with an acceptably low amount of these defects.

A major difficulty arising in the analysis of thick laminates is the computational impracticality of ply-by-ply structural analyses. Hence, methods to compute average properties of thick laminates for structural analyses are necessary to reduce the demands on computational facilities. Several theories for averaging the properties of thick laminates have appeared in the literature (1 - 4), but few of them have been actually verified with experimental data.

The objective of the present paper is to demonstrate a procedure for the manufacture of a high-quality, thick, gr/ep laminate, and to compare three-dimensional elastic stiffness predictions from a theory for thick laminates to experimentally measured stiffness components.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A 200-ply, [0/90]_{50S} laminate graphite/epoxy (Amoco T40-12K/ERLX-1962) was fabricated in a miniclave. Four type J thermocouples were inserted in the laminate to monitor the internal temperature distribution during the curing process (Fig.1). The laminate was placed in the miniclave mold and covered with bagging materials and an Al tool plate as shown in Fig. 2. The cure cycle recommended by the manufacturer and followed in this study is shown in Fig 3. A block of dimensions 43.2 x 27.3 x 27.0 mm in the 1, 2, and 3 directions, respectively, was carefully machined for the ultrasonic velocity measurements. A second specimen was fabricated in a similar manner with a [0]_{100T} stacking sequence to enable ultrasonic unidirectional elastic property measurements. The unidirectional material was machined into a block of dimension 23.1 x 38.2 x 12.7 mm in the 1, 2, and 3 directions, respectively, for the ultrasonic tests. Thin [0]_{8T} and [90]_{8T} laminates were also fabricated so that E_1 , E_2 , and ν_{21} could be measured quasi-statically. The engineering properties thereby determined were used in the analytical model when 3-D, quasi-static, effective laminate properties were to be calculated.

The dynamic, elastic stiffness components, C_{ij} , where $\sigma_i = C_{ij}\epsilon_j$, were measured ultrasonically using velocity and density measurements (5). Through-transmission measurements were employed with a pulser/receiver and matched pairs of contact transducers. The transducers used to generate longitudinal waves had center frequencies of 0.5, 1, 2.2, and 5 MHz. The shear wave transducers had center frequencies of 1 and 2.2 MHz. The wave phase speed (equal to the group velocity for wave propagation along directions of material symmetry) was determined by measuring the time required for a group of stress waves to travel through the material's thickness. The time of flight measurements were taken from the maximum peak of each pulse envelop.

The theory for plane wave propagation in homogeneous orthotropic media is available in many reference sources (6) and will not be repeated here. The material is assumed to be homogeneous and orthotropic, and the wave fronts are assumed to be planar. The nine nonzero, stiffness components of the cross-ply laminate are C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{33} , C_{44} , C_{55} , C_{66} ,

C_{12} , C_{13} , and C_{23} . The final expression for the stiffness components in terms of the velocities along the material's axes of symmetry is $C_{ij} = \rho V_{ij}^2$, where $i, j=1$ to 6. By measuring velocities of shear and longitudinal waves along the 1, 2, and 3 axes (i.e. normal incidence), we can determine the diagonal terms of the stiffness matrix, C_{ii} , where $i=1$ to 6 (5). The expressions describing wave propagation at arbitrary angles in the laminate are required to find the off-diagonal stiffness components, but these will not be used in this investigation.

Compression tests on small specimens machined from a portion of the thick laminate were carried out to obtain quasi-static engineering properties (7, 8). Young's modulus, and Poisson's ratio were determined using square cross-sectioned short-column specimens with length and width dimensions of 12.5 and 6.35 mm, respectively. Due to the limited amount of prepreg available for this study, only one specimen of each type could be tested and it must be understood that the results may not be statistically valid. Figure 4 shows the various strain gage (Micro Measurements CEA-06-032UW-120) locations and applied load directions. In all cases, the loading rate was 0.64 mm/minute.

3. MODIFIED LAMINATED PLATE THEORY

A modified laminated plate theory which includes out-of-plane properties was derived by Pagano (1). This theory is the same as the long-wave approximation described by Sun (3,4). The main assumptions of this theory are that the in-plane strains and out-of-plane stresses are uniform through the thickness of the laminate. We make the additional assumption here that all plies have identical transversely isotropic elastic properties. Suppose the constitutive equations of a constituent ply are written as

$$\sigma_i = C_{ij}\epsilon_j + C_{iA}\epsilon_j \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_A = C_{Aj}\epsilon_j + C_{AB}\epsilon_B \quad (2)$$

The subscripts i, j are associated with the in-plane coordinates and the subscripts A, B are associated with the out-of-plane coordinates. C's are the stiffness components. Introducing the in-plane stiffness matrix Q_{ij} ,

$$Q_{ij} = C_{ij} - C_{iA} C_{AB}^{-1} C_{Bj} \quad (3)$$

and noting that ϵ_j and σ_A are independent of the thickness coordinate z , one can derive the following laminate constitutive relations:

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \bar{Q}_{ij}\epsilon_j + \bar{T}_{iA}\sigma_A \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{\epsilon}_A = C_{AB}^{-1}\sigma_B + C_{AB}^{-1}C_{Bj}\epsilon_j \quad (5)$$

Here, an overbar stands for the average through the representative thickness h :

$$\bar{(\quad)} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\quad) dz \quad (6)$$

Further, T_{iA} is defined by

$$\bar{T}_{iA} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} C_{iB} C_{BA}^{-1} dz \quad (7)$$

Finally, Eq.(4) can be rearranged as

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = C_{ij}^* \varepsilon_j + C_{iA}^* \varepsilon_A \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_A = C_{Aj}^* \varepsilon_j + C_{AB}^* \bar{\varepsilon}_B \quad (9)$$

where C^* 's are the effective laminate stiffness. For the cross-ply laminate under consideration, Eq. (4) and (5) can be expressed in terms of the unidirectional properties as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11}^* = C_{22}^* &= \frac{1}{2m_1}(E_1 + E_2) + \frac{m_1}{m_2}E_2\bar{T}_{13}^2 & C_{12}^* &= \frac{1}{m_1}(E_2\nu_{12}) + \frac{m_1}{m_2}E_2\bar{T}_{13}^2 \\ C_{13}^* = C_{23}^* &= \frac{m_1}{m_2}E_2\bar{T}_{13} & C_{33}^* &= \frac{m_1}{m_2}E_2 \\ C_{44}^* = C_{55}^* &= \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} + \frac{1}{G_{23}} \right) \right\}^{-1} & C_{66}^* &= G_{12} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_{13} &= \frac{1}{2m_1}(\nu_{12} + \nu_{23} + \nu_{12}\nu_{23} + \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ m_1 &= 1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21} \quad \text{and} \quad m_2 = (1 + \nu_{23})(1 - \nu_{23} - 2\nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \end{aligned}$$

Input for the effective laminate properties described above are found by testing a simple, unidirectional sample. In our case, both ultrasonic and quasi-static properties were obtained in order to enable predictions of dynamic and static 3-D laminate properties. Subsequently, these predictions were compared with ultrasonic and quasi-static measurements carried out on the [0/90]_{50s} laminate.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermocouples embedded in the cross-ply laminate did not indicate any excessive temperature overshoot during the curing process (Fig. 5). Photomicrographs of a polished cross-section of the laminate revealed few voids, little fiber waviness, and negligible variation in fiber volume fraction through the thickness (Fig. 6). The cross-ply laminate had a density of 1590 kg/m³ and a fiber volume fraction of 59%.

Results of the ultrasonic measurements of C_{ij} for the unidirectional material are given in Table 1. In the ideal lamina we considered in the previous section, the stiffness components would satisfy the conditions of transverse isotropy. Note that this is not quite the case, however, as C_{22} is not equal to C_{33} , and C_{55} is not equal to C_{66} . This deviation from the assumed behavior could conceivably be caused by the nearly uniaxial pressure applied during processing. In order to properly use the model for laminates fabricated with transversely isotropic laminae, C_{22} and C_{33} were averaged, as were C_{55} and C_{66} (Table 2). Furthermore, since values of ν_{12} and ν_{23} were not measured for the unidirectional specimen, typical values of 0.30 and 0.49, respectively, were assumed. These Poisson's ratios, together with the averaged values for C_{22} , C_{33} , C_{55} , and C_{66} , were used to calculate the engineering properties for a transversely isotropic lamina. The off-diagonal C_{ij} terms could then be back-calculated. In this fashion, the entire set of stiffness constants and engineering properties for the lamina was determined (Table 2).

Results of the ultrasonic measurements of the longitudinal and shear wave velocities in the cross-ply laminates' principal material directions are given Table 3. In the directions dominated by fibers (V_{11} , V_{22}), longitudinal wave velocities decreased with higher frequencies (smaller wave lengths) due to dispersive effects within the nonhomogeneous laminate (9). Similar observations with longitudinal waves have been reported elsewhere (10,11). In the matrix dominated directions, the longitudinal wave speeds were nearly constant. The shear wave velocities were also constant for the two test frequencies with particle motions in the 2-3 and 1-3 planes. Due to excessive pulse distortion, the wave speed V_{55} corresponding to C_{55} could not be determined with the 1 MHz shear transducer. The stiffness measurements based on several insonation frequencies were *averaged* and tabulated in Tables 3 and 4.

Predictions of C_{ij} and the engineering elastic constants from the three-dimensional analysis are given in Table 4 along with the averaged C_{ij} determined from ultrasonic tests. The in-plane stiffnesses were predicted to be higher than the measurements, while the out-of-plane stiffnesses were predicted to be lower than the measurements. Much of these discrepancies can be attributed to the dispersive nature of laminated fiber composites, whereby the measured stiffness depends on the wavelength of the stress wave. Being a long-wave analysis, the 3-D analysis does not account for dispersion. The values of C_{11} and C_{22} measured with the 0.5 MHz longitudinal transducers agreed very well with the predictions, even though the predictions were based on lamina elastic constants determined with 5 MHz longitudinal transducers and 2.25 MHz shear wave transducers. This was probably due to the wavelength of the 0.5 MHz transducers approaching the long-wave assumption of the theory.

To enable comparison of the short column, quasi-static test data with analytical predictions, it was necessary to first provide quasi-static elastic properties for input to the model. Values of E_1 , E_2 , and ν_{21} measured with the 8-ply tensile specimens were used for this purpose, along with other typical values taken from the literature (Table 5). As before, transverse isotropy at the ply level was assumed. Table 5 also includes a comparison of predicted and measured quasi-static, effective laminate engineering constants. The measured in-plane moduli, E_1 and E_2 , are slightly lower than the predictions, but the measured out-of-plane modulus, E_3 , is higher than the predicted value. The measured Poisson's ratios do not appear to be accurate. The out-of-plane Poisson's ratios, ν_{13} and ν_{23} , should be nearly equal for cross-ply laminates, and ν_{12} seems too high. Due to the many possible sources of error in transverse strain measurements with anisotropic materials (namely, gage misalignment and compressive loading misalignment), the measured Poisson's ratios are highly suspect.

5. SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A 200-ply, [0/90]_{50S}, graphite/epoxy laminate was fabricated in a miniclave. Photomicrographic examinations showed good quality throughout the thickness. Mechanical

testing of miniature specimens and ultrasonic testing of the bulk material were used to measure the quasi-static and dynamic three-dimensional elastic properties of the material. 3-D elastic constants predicted by a modified laminated plate analysis were in good overall agreement with the experimentally determined values. In future work, it will be necessary to further develop reliable ultrasonic test methods to determine the mechanical properties of thick composites. In particular, the transition of material response from short-wave to long-wave behavior needs to be examined closely.

6. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1. Raw ultrasonic stiffness measurements (GPa).

Laminate	C ₁₁	C ₂₂	C ₃₃	C ₄₄	C ₅₅	C ₆₆
[0] ₁₀₀ T	165*	14.0*	14.3*	3.53**	5.74**	6.36**
[0/90] ₅₀ S	75.9+	74.7+	13.1+	4.1**	4.1**	5.2**

* 5 MHz; ** 2.2 MHz; + Avg. all frequencies tested.

TABLE 2. Ultrasonic stiffness constants and engineering properties for a transversely isotropic lamina of T40/ERLX-1962.

Stiffness (GPa)								
C ₁₁	C ₂₂	C ₃₃	C ₄₄	C ₅₅	C ₆₆	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₂₃
165*	14.2*	14.2*	3.53*	6.05*	6.05*	6.34**	6.34**	7.03**
Engineering Properties (GPa, for moduli) **								
E ₁	E ₂	E ₃	G ₂₃	G ₁₃	G ₁₂	ν ₁₂	ν ₁₃	ν ₂₃
162	10.5	10.5	3.53	6.05	6.05	0.30	0.30	0.49

* Measured; ** Calculated, assuming transverse isotropy.

TABLE 3. Ultrasonic velocity measurements and stiffness calculations for cross-ply laminate.

Velocity (km/sec)						Elastic Stiffness (GPa)					
Vel.	0.5 (MHz)	1.0 (MHz)	2.2 (MHz)	5.0 (MHz)	Ave. Vel.	C _{ij}	0.5 (MHz)	1.0 (MHz)	2.2 (MHz)	5.0 (MHz)	Ave. C _{ij}
V ₁₁	7.50	7.08	6.91	6.07	6.89	C ₁₁	89.4	79.6	76.0	58.6	75.9
V ₂₂	7.56	7.00	6.63	6.15	6.84	C ₂₂	90.9	77.9	70.0	60.0	74.7
V ₃₃	2.92	2.83	2.85	2.87	2.87	C ₃₃	13.6	12.8	12.9	13.1	13.1
V ₄₄	-	1.6	1.6	-	1.6	C ₄₄	-	4.1	4.1	-	4.1
V ₅₅	-	1.6	1.6	-	1.6	C ₅₅	-	4.1	4.1	-	4.1
V ₆₆	-	-	1.8	-	1.8	C ₆₆	-	-	5.2		5.2

TABLE 4. Effective ultrasonic stiffness measurements and predictions (GPa).

	C ₁₁	C ₂₂	C ₃₃	C ₄₄	C ₅₅	C ₆₆	C ₂₃	C ₃₁	C ₁₂
Model	90.2	90.2	14.1	4.46	4.46	6.06	6.68	6.68	6.34
Ultra-sonic	75.9	74.7	13.1	4.1	4.1	5.2	-	-	-
	E ₁	E ₂	E ₃	v ₁₂	v ₂₃	v ₁₃			
Model	87.0	87.0	13.2	0.037	0.46	0.46			
Com-pression	73.3	70.6	14.9	0.13	0.73	0.43			

TABLE 5. Quasi-static engineering properties.

	E ₁ (GPa)	E ₂ (GPa)	E ₃ (GPa)	v ₁₂	v ₂₃	v ₁₃	
Input to Model	160*	7.48*	7.48+	0.33*	0.49**	0.33+	(lamina)
Model	84.0	84.0	9.45	0.03	0.48	0.48	(laminate)
Test Result	73.3	70.6	14.9	0.13	0.73	0.43	(laminate)

* Measured on 8-ply specimens (3 each)

** Taken from literature (3)

+ Assumed value for transversely isotropic lamina

Thermocouple 1: On top surface Thermocouple 2: 6.4 mm below top surface
 Thermocouple 3: 12.4 mm below top surface Thermocouple 4: Between laminate and tool

FIGURE 1. Position of thermocouples inserted in the laminates (cutaway shown for convenience).

FIGURE 2. Schematic lay-up of thick graphite/epoxy laminate in a miniclave .

FIGURE 3. Cure cycle of the thick graphite/epoxy laminate.

FIGURE 4. Compression test specimens and strain gage orientations: Specimen A for E_1, ν_{12} ; Specimen B for E_2, ν_{23} ; Specimen C for E_3, ν_{31} .

FIGURE 5. Temperature distribution across thickness of laminate during cure.

(a) ply no. 25

(b) ply no. 102

(c) ply no. 175

FIGURE 6. Representative photomicrographs of a cross-section of the 200-ply laminate: (a) Ply no. 25 (near top); (b) Ply no. 102; (c) Ply no. 175 (near bottom).